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Glycyrrhizin and Coronaviruses

Domina Petric, MD

ABSTRACT

The SARS-CoV-2 is a novel β -coronavirus, which is enveloped non-segmented positive-sense RNA virus that causes COVID-19 disease.

Few studies showed that glycyrrhizin from liquorice root has some anti-viral effect on coronaviruses, what opens the question can glycyrrhizin be used as experimental drug for the treatment of COVID-19 patients or can this compound lead to the development of similar, more potent drugs. Another interesting compound is resveratrol (from grape seeds and red wine) that is available as 200 mg capsules for which has been found that has some *in vitro* anti-viral effect on coronaviruses too.

INTRODUCTION

In late December 2019, a cluster of unexplained pneumonia cases has been reported in Wuhan, China. A few days later, the causative agent of this mysterious pneumonia was identified as a novel coronavirus. This causative virus has been temporarily named as severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) and the relevant infected disease has been named as coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) by the World Health Organization respectively. The COVID-19 epidemic is spreading in China and all over the world now¹.

SARS-CoV-2

The SARS-CoV-2 is a β -coronavirus, which is enveloped non-segmented positive-sense RNA virus (subgenus *sarbecovirus*, subfamily *Orthocoronavirinae*²).

It was found that the genome sequence of SARS-CoV-2 is 96.2% identical to a bat CoV RaTG13, whereas it shares 79.5% identity to SARS-CoV. Based on virus genome sequencing results and evolutionary analysis, bat has been

suspected as natural host of virus origin, and SARS-CoV-2 might be transmitted from bats via unknown intermediate hosts to infect humans³.

The novel coronavirus uses the same receptor, angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) as that for SARS-CoV, and mainly spreads through the respiratory tract. Importantly, increasingly evidence showed sustained human-to-human transmission, along with many exported cases across the globe. The clinical symptoms of COVID-19 patients include fever, cough, fatigue and a small population of patients appeared gastrointestinal infection symptoms. The elderly and people with underlying diseases are susceptible to infection and prone to serious outcomes, which may be associated with acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and cytokine storm⁴.

ANTIVIRAL TREATMENTS

Scientists previously confirmed that the protease inhibitors lopinavir and ritonavir, used to treat infection with human immunodeficiency virus (HIV⁵), could improve the outcome of MERS-CoV⁶ and SARS-CoV⁷ patients.

It has reported that β -coronavirus viral loads of a COVID-19 patient in Korea significantly decreased after

lopinavir/ritonavir (Kaletra®, AbbVie, North Chicago, IL, USA) treatment⁸.

Additionally, clinicians combined Chinese and Western medicine treatment including lopinavir/ritonavir (Kaletra®), arbidol, and Shufeng Jiedu Capsule (SFJDC, a traditional Chinese medicine) and gained significant improvement in pneumonia associated symptoms in Shanghai Public Health Clinical Center, China⁹.

The other antiviral drugs that can be potentially used for the treatment of COVID-19 patients include chloroquine, remdesivir, nafamostat, ribavirin, oseltamivir, penciclovir/acyclovir, ganciclovir, favipiravir and nitazoxanide⁴.

GLYCYRRHIZIN

Cinatl and coworkers (2003) assessed the antiviral potential of ribavirin, 6-azauridine, pyrazofurin, mycophenolic acid, and glycyrrhizin (an active component of liquorice roots) against two clinical isolates of coronavirus (FFM-1 and FFM-2) from patients with SARS admitted to the clinical center of Frankfurt University, Germany. Of all the compounds, glycyrrhizin was the most active in inhibiting replication of the SARS-associated virus. Their findings suggest that glycyrrhizin should be assessed for treatment of SARS¹⁰.

Other studies showed that *in vitro* glycyrrhizin (a constituent of liquorice root), resveratrol (in grape seeds and red wine), silvestrol, and baicalin have been found to have some anti-viral effect on coronaviruses¹¹⁻¹³.

CONCLUSION

Some studies showed that glycyrrhizin from liquorice root has some anti-viral effect on coronaviruses, what opens the question can glycyrrhizin be used as experimental drug for the treatment of COVID-19 patients or can this compound lead to the development of similar, more potent drugs.

Another interesting compound is resveratrol (from grape seeds and red wine) that is available as 200 mg capsules (Solgar Resveratrol®): it has been found that resveratrol has some *in vitro* anti-viral effect on coronaviruses too.

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